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PHOTO ART PROJECT "FIRST RAY"

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ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ «ПЕРШИЙ ПРОМІНЬ»

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The "First Ray" project was launched in 2009. According to the idea and concept developed, the shooting takes place in the high mountain systems of the Himalayas, Karakoram, and the Cordillera at dawn. The shooting aims to capture the first rays of the sun illuminating the snow-capped mountain peaks. A prerequisite for shooting is no later than two minutes after the first touch of the sun's ray to the peak. Since the sun is still deep below the horizon at this time, the lighting at the shooting point corresponds to twilight conditions, although the subject is in daylight conditions. This provides additional opportunities for creative reinterpretation of the scene and presentation of the result as an art object. The prerequisites for achieving the result are that the photographer should be located mostly at an altitude of 4000 metres. The height of the peaks to be photographed is from 6500 metres above sea level. The exposition is arranged according to the light, which allows for detail and draws the viewer's attention to the idea of the project. Additionally, to enhance the impression, the sky was "dulled" in post-processing until details and colour disappeared completely.

Photo No. 1

Ama Dablam peak, Himalayas, Nepal.
View from the village of Tengboche.
2012.

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Mamiya-Sekor C 210 mm f/4

Settings:

210 mm | F11 | ISO 100 | 1/25 s

**Image No. 1 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Photo No. 2

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 5D Mark II /
Canon EF 70-200 f/4 + Extender 1.4x

Settings:

288 mm | F14 | ISO 320 | 1/60 s

**Image No. 2 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Ama Dablam peak, Himalayas, Nepal.
View from the top of Kala Patar.
2009.

Photo No. 3

Kongde Ri mountain range, Himalayas, Nepal. View from the village of Namche Bazar. 2012.

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Mamiya-Sekor C 80 mm f/2.8

Settings:

80 mm | F11 | ISO 100 | 1/15 s

**Image No. 3 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Photo No. 4

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Mamiya-Sekor C 80 mm f/2.8

Settings:

80 mm | F11 | ISO 200 | 1/80 s

**Image No. 4 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

The peak of Fari Lapcha, Himalayas, Nepal. View from the top of Gokyo Ri. 2012.

Photo No. 5

Kantega and Tamserku peaks, Himalayas, Nepal. View from the village of Kumchung. 2012.

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Mamiya-Sekor C 80 mm f/2.8

Settings:

80 mm | F8 | ISO 100 | 1/200 s

**Image No. 5 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

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Photo No. 6

South Anapurna Peak, Himalayas, Nepal. View from the Poon Hill.
2019.

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Pentax 67 165 mm f/2.8

Settings:

165 mm | F8 | ISO 50 | 1/3 s

**Image No. 6 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Photo No. 7

Dhaulagiri Peak, Himalayas, Nepal.
View from the Poon Hill.
2019.

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Pentax 67 165 mm f/2.8

Settings:

165 mm | F8 | ISO 50 | 1/20 s

**Image No. 7 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Photo No. 8

Camera / Lens

Phase One AFD II P45+ /
Pentax 67 165 mm f/2.8

Settings:

165 mm | F8 | ISO 50 | 1/59 s

**Image No. 8 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Machapuchre Peak, Himalayas, Nepal.
View from the Poon Hill.
2019.

Photo No. 9

Chohori Peak – K2, Karakoram, Pakistan. View from the Concordia Plateau. 2021.

Camera / Lens

Phase One XF IQ3 100 MP /
Pentax 67 165 mm f/2.8

Settings:

165 mm | F8 | ISO 50 | 1/13 s

**Image No. 9 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

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Photo No. 10

Masebrum Peak, Karakoram, Pakistan. View from the Baltoro glacier. 2021.

Camera / Lens

Phase One XF IQ3 100 MP /
Pentax 67 165 mm f/2.8

Settings:

165 mm | F8 | ISO 50 | 1/180 s

**Image No. 10 editing with
Adobe Photoshop**

Filter:

neutral grey ND500+ND16